

BB-2208: HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

2nd Individual Assignment 2

**MARSYA FARM
(THE WARWICK MODEL)**

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Abstract

This aim of this paper is to better understand Marsya Farm and The Warwick model. It begins with providing a general introduction of the company with a problem statement regarding Marsya Farm business. The paper also describes what is The Warwick model which could help the farming business better understand HRM model strategy for the business sustainability, success and growth which can also help to achieve maximum organizational goals. Finally, the paper concludes with a recommendation for Marsya Farm.

Executive Summary

Marsya Farm is a business that has been at the forefront of agricultural progress, experimenting with more traditional approaches as well as modern innovations such as drip irrigation, fertigation, hydroponics, and rain shelter based atop a 2.8-hectare plantation of land. Marsya Farm is currently cultivating a variety of crops in Kawasan Kemajuan Pertanian which is also known as KKP at Kampung Sungai Liang in Daerah Belait. The farm currently grows several crops, including, among many others, fruits such as menas and mulberry, and vegetables such as mustard leaf, cucumbers, cherry tomato, and corn. The founder and manager of Marsya Farm, Awang Haji Muliadi bin Moxsin began his farming business in the year 2009 with only 1-hectare wide of land. In 2004, he began to expand his farm business by another hectare and in 2014, he again expanded another 0.8 hectare of land. In 2016, Marsya Farm managed to harvest its production of about 73 tonnes of weight. As what has been achieved, Marsya Farm hopes the company will be able to increase its production and distribution. Marsya Farm distributes their products to 13 location of companies which are, Supa Save in Mabohai, Beribi and Seria; Soon Lee Megamart in Gadong, Berakas, Pandan 7 Belait, Seaview Kuala Belait and Sunagi Liang; Hua Ho Department Stores in Tanjung Bunut and Manggis Mall and lasty, Yellow Cab Pizzeria in Serusop and Kiulap. Furthermore, Awang Haji Muliadi seeks to further collaborate with the Department of Agriculture and Agri Food to promote 'contract farming' which would attract younger farmers which also sustain national food supply and security. In the beginning, Marsya Farm did not have a financial start-up by the bank. However, he had to resort to some family members and close friends to lend him money. He also lacked support and encouragement when starting his business but hope and blessing, he was determined and enabled him to be successful

as what he has achieved today. It took some time for Marsya Farm to be where it is now, he lacked knowledge and expertise regarding farming business as there were many trials and errors. However, using the Warwick model could help the farming business better understand HRM model strategy for the business sustainability, success and growth which can also help to achieve maximum organizational goals.

Problem Statement

At start, Marsya Farm had problems starting its business. It would be incredibly useful if there was some monetary funding to start the farm company. However, the bank would not consider Awang Haji Muliadi's offer for a loan including equity and other conditions, such as being able to meet its maturity deadlines and the minimum amount payable. Some family members and close friends had to turn to Awang Haji Muliadi to lend him money to start his farm business. When he started his farming business, the farm company lacked support and encouragement when he remembered that there was little motivation and first decided to move into agriculture and begin farming industry. Marsya Farm has a lack of knowledge and expertise in the matter of farming and agriculture industry. Awang Haji Muliadi had to further upgrade his skills on his own and learn how to manage his business. The farming business also lacks technology and knowledge, he took a long time to adapt and learnt as technology nowadays has a greater impact and affect to every business.

The Warwick Model

The Human Resource Management model provides an analytical framework for studying HRM. Having analyzed the HRM models described business sustainability, success and growth for the business. According to Armstrong (2014), Human resources management is characterized as a strategic, integrated and coherent approach to the employment in the organization. The Warwick model was constructed by the researchers Chris Hendry and Andrew M. Pettigrew at the University of Warwick in the early 1900s. This model focuses on Human Resources management's analytical style where it can also consider the impact of the role of personnel functions on the content of the human resource policy. The Warwick proposition, among other

models, focuses on five which include the outer context (macro environmental forces), the context of the inner (firm specific or micro environmental force), the organization or business-strategy content, HRM context and HRM content.

This Warwick Model takes cognizance of business strategy and HR practices which shows the integration of organizational strategy of the inner context and outer context. As such, for recruitment and selection, the model has relevance, seeing that internal and external contexts can be combined with organizational strategy. In turn, organizational strategy impacts HRM practices and influences it. Systems, processes, procedures, techniques, approaches and methods are used in such practices. The strength of the Warwick model is primarily focused on the fact that it identifies and classifies significant environmental influences on HRM. It also shows the relations between the environment and organizational strategy. In addition, this model discusses how HRM can respond to the changes in the external environment. As can be seen at figure 1, it shows the context and contents of the Warwick model which consists of external and internal environmental factors which affect HRM functions.

The Warwick Model

Figure 1 – The Warwick Model

The above HRM model illustrates how the outer context of social economic, technological, political-legal factors and legal factors influence and impact the organization's inner context. The inner context consists of the culture, structure, politics/leadership, task-technology and business output. The inner context influences and affects the outer context (role definition, organization and HR output), as well as the content of an organization's (business) strategy.

Recommendations

In term of business strategy context, Marsya Farm should prepare early exposure in the farming business whereby to start the business, he should upgrade his skills on his own or collect data or knowledge regarding farming industry and how to operate a farming business in Brunei. With this strategy, he can further his skills on his own and learn how to manage his business properly without anyone giving encouragement and knowledge during his time in early farming business. Marsya Farm could become a role model to the agriculture and farming industry in such a program where interested agripreneurs can sign up to and receive guidance from mentors who have already established a strong foothold in this industry. Once the agripreneurs are deemed ready to be on their own, their business ideas should be invested in and the government can provide some financial backing for these ideas to be realized.

In the inner context, task technology is most important for the organization of the farming and agriculture industry. Without Knowledge and expertise, the business will fail but if he could manage to find any workers specialize in certain areas such as checking soil suitability, able to update the latest technology in farming areas, monitor crop health and many more. With knowledge or expertise of workers, it can help the farming business more efficiently and effectively. Drone technology has its potential in agriculture such that drones can be used to monitor crop health, soil health, soil humidity levels, or to detect crop and weed data. These uses for drones are exciting technologies that can save a farmer time when applied and can increase the overall health of their crops. It also can improve yields while saving the producer time, energy and allowing them to more efficiently use soil enhancers and fertilizer. Therefore, Marsya Farm could use this technology in the future. There are now numerous livestock GPS tracking

applications that can assist in many ways and provide substantial details. Applying this in Marysa Farm can track and monitor every crop they produce.

References

1. Armstrong, M, (2014) Armstrong's' Hand book of Human Resource Management Practice, 13th Edition. UK, Ashford Colour Press Ltd.
2. Musa, S. F. P. D. H., Pg Hj Idris, P. S. R., & Basir, K. H. (2020). Inspiring Agripreneurs of Brunei. UNISSA Press, Universiti Islam Sultan Sharif Ali.
3. Station, P. 6 Emerging Technologies in Agriculture. , from <https://www.princessroyal.com.au/blog/6-emerging-technologies-in-agriculture>
4. Storey, J. (1987) 'Developments in the management of human resources: an interim report',
5. Warwick Papers in Industrial Relations, 17, IRRU, School of Industrial and Business Studies, University of Warwick